

Impact of Branding On Consumer Purchase Decision

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Abstract

This paper is about studying the impact of branding on consumer purchase decisions. Brand affiliation put a high impact on consumer buying patterns. Now, the consumer is more knowledgeable about various brands and factors such as price, quality, value, and other factors. Brands create a sense of status in society so consumers are now starting to use various brands according to the trends or fashion. The consumer wants a sense of recognition that's why they prefer to buy branded products or expensive products over non-branded ones to show their status. The sense of status gives recognition in society, family, and friends that make the consumer happy. Branding is imperative marketing through which observation of buying behavior of consumers and their viewpoint towards brands can be studied. The purchasing decision towards brands is also affected by the nature of the consumer, age factor, income, gender, or personality traits. The word loyalty also comes in branding if consumers are fully loyal to branded products then he/she may prefer brands over brands. Branding association can affect organizations in a positive or negatively way, if brand image is positive then consumers prefer to buy products and repeats purchases also. But if there is negative image of the brand in the eyes of consumers then there will be no repetition of purchases and retention of consumers. So firms incur huge amount of expenditure on the advertisement to maintain their brand image and also organizes brand equity management programs.

Keywords: - Brand Association, Consumer buying behavior, Imperative marketing.

Introduction

Branding is important for any business. Brand Association put a great impact on customer choice. Now, Consumer is aware of brand knowledge. Studying the behavior of consumers is generally significant for marketers. Studying the nature or behavior of consumers provides a way to understand what way consumer make their purchases. A good brand image and brand awareness lead to good brand knowledge which in turn. The higher the brand knowledge, the higher will be the consumer's concern about the reliability of the brand. Consumers prefer branded products over ordinary products and customers think that branded products are more durable and can be used for extended periods of your time. A brand enhances product quality by highlighting various opportunities that make the products more attractive and better. If a company wants to manage their brands, then it should have to fulfill the desires and wishes of the consumers. The brand is a sense of recognition that makes or changes the consumer's decision in favor of a product or a brand. Now the market become too much competitive, with this

competition in the market is arises. If you want to compete in this market, you should have to develop a strong brand image. Brand image is an image that a consumer has specific concerns about the brand and reaction to the brand in the market places. Consumers are more status conscious and they always prefer to buy branded products over non-branded ones. It is always seen that behavior of the consumers toward branded products or services is based on their age, gender, and personality traits. This study is aimed at analyzing the behavior of consumers toward purchasing branded products and services and what factors or attributes they consider while making their purchases. If we talk about modern society, brands not only represent the company but have also a strong attachment to the product's quality, social class, taste, etc. Branding is a key tool that helps create customer value, creating and maintaining competitive advantage.

Literature Review

Literature Review

There have been various researches (Fatima Sarwar, 2014) have been conducted by the researchers to study the purchasing patterns of the customers. Marketers use brands to gain a competitive edge in the market and for long term success for the organisation. (Kunal Kshirsagar, 2020). These researches shows that there are various factors that are need to be considered while studying the buying behaviour of the customers. Various factors such as price, quality, quantity, branding power, marketing strategies and design of the retail store and its layout influence the purchasing power of the customers. In this study, we are considering the **BRANDING** as an imperative factor that changes the purchasing behaviour of the customers. If successfully branding strategies is planned, then the customers have positive viewpoint towards that retail store, and they repetition their purchases.

Objectives

The main objective of the study is to examine the impact of branding on customer purchase decision. Some of the objectives of the study are under as follows:-

1. To study the preference of customers towards branded products over unbranded products.
2. To study consumer perception towards branded products.

Type Of Study

Primary Data is collected for this study through survey method. A questionnaire is designed and necessary or relevant information is collected that are useful for the study. A Close ended questionnaire is made, alternative choice are provided to respondents. A questionnaire is designed in such a way that provide basis to the objectives of the study. Clear and easily understandable questions are used to prepare the questionnaire so that everyone can give the answers properly. Secondary information is also used to study the questions that are need to be asked while making questionnaire so that all objectives of the study can be achieved.

Data Interpretation And Analysis

This Study is based on the 40 responses.

Interpretation

1. In this Study, we find out that there are highly number of customers are brand loyal i.e 71.8% customers are loyal towards brand.
2. There are different attributes such as such as Brand Name, Transparency, Cleanliness and price are responsible that persuade customers to buy branded products but 60% of the customers choose brand name attribute while purchasing.
3. In this study, we analyse that the main reason delay between actual purchase and purchase decision is financial Constraints i.e 53.8%. Customers choose financial constraints as a reason for delay in purchasing of branded products.
4. It is to be noted that 59% customers switch over brand preference from one to another brand if they get better promotional schemes.
5. We find out that the customers are become aware as well as conscious towards their purchase decision, they wait for market responses and for more innovative products.
6. Quality is the main factor that encourage customers to buy branded products i.e. 56.4%
7. In this era, Youth always goes on the path of their idols or follow them i.e. celebrities, cricketers or the singers. And in this we find out that 69.2% customers believe that products advertise by the celebrities are of a good quality.
8. Now, Customers are become more aware towards their purchases, they like to do experiment different brands i.e. around 71.8% customers do experiment among brands while purchasing.

9. In this study, we analyse that 92.3% respondents believe that sponsorship help companies to build strong brand image.

Findings

1. It is to be found that most of the customers prefer branded products because of the attribute of quality.
2. It is also found that financial constraint is the factor persuade the customers not to buy the products whichever they like.
3. In India, most of the population is in between 15-25 and 25-35 age criteria. So, it is found that our youth is highly attracted towards branded products rather than non-branded.
4. So, based on the results found by this survey, customers are now becoming more brand conscious and stick loyal towards Particular Brands.

Limitations

1. Most of the respondent in the study is College students or working class people. So, it may not be possible to generalize the finding to the entire population of the

country.

2. Close ended questionnaire is used for collecting responses. This cannot help in getting customer opinions and comments.
3. In this study, the size of universe or population taken into account is small. So, every type of population criteria is not included in this study.
4. The information provided by some of the respondents is not true.

References

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